

How Office Layouts Influence Software Development?

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SLR – List of Findings And Correlations

Study Ref.	Environment Type	Dimension	Group of Characteristics	Characteristics	Effect	Outcome Category	Outcome
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located development work	+	Communication	Communication quality
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	Physical	Software Engineering Practices	Face-to-face communication	Face-to-face communication	+	Communication	Reliability of Information
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Task board	Task board	+	Communication	Stakeholders communication
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located development work	+	Customer	Customer relationship
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Collective meetings	Scrum Meetings	+	Organization	Geographical and physical barriers
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Pair programming	Pair programming	+	Organization	Geographical and physical barriers
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Collective meetings	Scrum Meetings	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Collective meetings	Scrum Meetings	+	Personnel	Individual work and problem-solving
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Collective meetings	Scrum Meetings	+	Personnel	Work efficiency
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located development work	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Team members working in the same office or on the same level of the building	+	Personnel	Confidence at work
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	Physical	Software Engineering Practices	Face-to-face communication	Face-to-face communication	+	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information

(AHMAD et al., 2018)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Job rotation	Exchange of Team Members	+	Personnel	People Interaction
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Pair programming	Pair programming	+	Personnel	Individual commitment
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	TDD	Test Driven Development	+	Personnel	Individual work and problem-solving
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	Virtual	Support Tool	Video Conference	Video Conference	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	Physical	Software Engineering Practices	Face-to-face communication	Face-to-face communication	+	Product	Required quality
(AHMAD et al., 2018)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Documentation	Use of Code documentation	+	Prerequisites	Project tools and artifacts
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Combi	Combi Office	-	Management	Leadership
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Flex Office	+	Management	Leadership
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Large open plan (>24 persons/room)	-	Management	Leadership
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Small open plan (4 to 9 persons/room)	-	Management	Leadership
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Private rooms	Shared room office (2 to 3 people share a single room)	+	Management	Leadership
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Flex Office	+	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Performance
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Privacy
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Self-organization
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Worker general health

(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Worker general satisfaction
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Worker mental health
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Combi	Combi Office	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Combi	Combi Office	+	Personnel	Performance
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Combi	Combi Office	+	Personnel	Self-organization
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Combi	Combi Office	-	Personnel	Worker general satisfaction
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Flex Office	+	Personnel	Performance
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Flex Office	+	Personnel	Privacy
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Flex Office	-	Personnel	Privacy
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Flex Office	+	Personnel	Worker general health
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Large open plan (>24 persons/room)	-	Personnel	Worker general health
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Medium-sized open plan (10 to 24 persons/room)	-	Personnel	Collaboration
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Medium-sized open plan (10 to 24 persons/room)	-	Personnel	Performance
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Medium-sized open plan (10 to 24 persons/room)	-	Personnel	Worker general health
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Medium-sized open plan (10 to 24 persons/room)	+	Personnel	Worker general satisfaction
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Small open plan (4 to 9 persons/room)	-	Personnel	Individual work and problem-solving
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Small open plan (4 to 9 persons/room)	-	Personnel	People Interaction
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Small open plan (4 to 9 persons/room)	-	Personnel	Performance
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Small open plan (4 to 9 persons/room)	+	Personnel	Work efficiency
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Small open plan (4 to 9 persons/room)	-	Personnel	Worker general health

(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Private rooms	Shared room office (2 to 3 people share a single room)	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Private rooms	Shared room office (2 to 3 people share a single room)	+	Personnel	Performance
(DANIELSSON; BODIN, 2008)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Private rooms	Shared room office (2 to 3 people share a single room)	-	Personnel	Worker general health
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Business	Construction costs
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Shared Spaces	Hoteling	+	Business	Accommodation costs
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Remote working	Tele-working and homeworking	+	Business	Accommodation costs
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Hot-desking	+	Communication	Communication quality
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Meeting Spaces	Social Meeting spaces	+	Communication	Informal communication
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Communication	Communication quality
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Communication	Informal communication
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	N/A	Office Design Practices	Autocratic	Office redesign by managers own interpretations	-	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	N/A	Office Design Practices	Cooperative	Cooperation with teamworkers for the development of office space	+	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Organization	Organizational structure
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	N/A	Office Design Practices	Socio-technical	Socio-technical approach to design and management of workspace	+	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Combi	Mix of diferent spaces	+	Personnel	People Interaction

(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	N/A	Office Design Practices	Cooperative	Cooperation with teamworkers for the development of office space	+	Personnel	Worker general satisfaction
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	People Interaction
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Personnel	People Interaction
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Personnel	Privacy
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Personnel	Worker general satisfaction
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Personnel	Worker mental health
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Personnel	Worker mental health
(DAVIS; LEACH; CLEGG, 2011)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Remote working	Tele-working and homeworking	+	Personnel	Worker general satisfaction
(GIRAY et al., 2018)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(GIRAY et al., 2018)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(GIRAY et al., 2018)	Physical	Software Engineering Practices	Face-to-face communication	Face-to-face communication	+	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(GIRAY et al., 2018)	Physical	Software Engineering Practices	Team characteristics and abilities	High skilled team	+	Personnel	Performance
(GIRAY et al., 2018)	Physical	Software Engineering Practices	Team characteristics and abilities	High skilled team	+	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(GIRAY et al., 2018)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Team commitment

(GIRAY et al., 2018)	Physical	Software Engineering Practices	Team characteristics and abilities	High skilled team	+	Personnel	Problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Physical	Macro-Environment	Multiple teams	Team areas are in conjunction	+	Communication	Open communication
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Physical	Macro-Environment	Multiple teams	Team areas are in conjunction	+	Management	Work visibility
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	N/A	Office Design Practices	Cooperative	Cooperation with the Facilities Operations & Maintenance for the development of office space	+	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	N/A	Office Design Practices	Participative	Individual user discussions about new team areas	+	Organization	Organizational feedback
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Virtual	Support Tool	Video Conference	Video Conference	+	Organization	Cooperation between sites
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	People seating together	+	Personnel	Problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	People seating together	+	Personnel	Team commitment
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Common areas	Common areas	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Documentation	Wikis	+	Personnel	Availability of project information, discussions or instructions
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Radiators	+	Personnel	Team commitment
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Job rotation	Exchange of Team Members	+	Personnel	People Interaction
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Physical	Macro-Environment	Multiple teams	Multiple teamwork environment	+	Personnel	Work efficiency
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Physical	Macro-Environment	Multiple teams	Team areas are in conjunction	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	N/A	Office Design Practices	Participative	Individual user discussions about new team areas	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Virtual	Support Tool	Chat room	Chat rooms	+	Personnel	Availability of project information, discussions or instructions

(HALLIKAINEN, 2011)	Physical	Software Engineering Practices	Multitasking	Team members with different work tasks	-	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(HUA et al., 2010)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Common areas	Amenity-related Spaces (shared kitchen or coffee areas) with longer distances to workstations	+	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(HUA et al., 2010)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Common areas	Amenity-related Spaces (shared kitchen or coffee areas) with occupants in nearby workstations	+	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(HUA et al., 2010)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Common areas	Service-Related Spaces (shared print/copy areas)	-	Personnel	Collaboration
(HUA et al., 2010)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Common areas	Service-Related Spaces (shared print/copy areas)	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection
(HUA et al., 2010)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Common areas	Service-Related Spaces (shared print/copy areas)	-	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(HUA et al., 2010)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Common areas	Service-Related Spaces (shared print/copy areas) with copiers in dedicated hubs	+	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(HUA et al., 2010)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Common areas	Service-Related Spaces (shared print/copy areas) with shorter distance from the workstation to the shared service area	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(HUA et al., 2010)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Meeting Spaces	Teamwork Related Spaces (Meeting Spaces)	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(HUA et al., 2010)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Meeting Spaces	Teamwork Related Spaces (Meeting Spaces) with close to neighborhoods of workstations	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(HUA et al., 2010)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Meeting Spaces	Teamwork Related Spaces (Meeting Spaces) with meeting rooms located around the core or at the corners of a floor plate	+	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(HUMMEL; ROSENKRANZ; HOLTEN, 2015)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	On-site customer	On-Site Customer	+	Communication	Communication Quality

(HUMMEL; ROSENKRANZ; HOLTEN, 2015)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	On-site customer	On-Site Customer	+	Customer	Customer relationship
(HUMMEL; ROSENKRANZ; HOLTEN, 2015)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located teamwork	+	Organization	Geographical and physical barriers
(HUMMEL; ROSENKRANZ; HOLTEN, 2015)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located teamwork	+	Personnel	Work efficiency
(HUMMEL; ROSENKRANZ; HOLTEN, 2015)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	On-site customer	On-Site Customer	+	Personnel	Cooperation
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Collaborative spaces with unassigned desks (Agile Offices)	+	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	People Interaction
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Individual work and problem-solving
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Collaborative spaces with unassigned desks (Agile Offices)	+	Personnel	Individual work and problem-solving
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Collaborative spaces with unassigned desks (Agile Offices)	+	Personnel	Mobility
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Collaborative spaces with unassigned desks (Agile Offices)	-	Personnel	People Interaction
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Collaborative spaces with unassigned desks (Agile Offices)	-	Personnel	Privacy
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Collaborative spaces with unassigned desks (Agile Offices)	-	Personnel	Team awareness

(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Collaborative spaces with unassigned desks (Agile Offices)	-	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Personnel	Individual work and problem-solving
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Personnel	People Interaction
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Prerequisites	Project tools and artifacts
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Flexibility	Collaborative spaces with unassigned desks (Agile Offices)	+	Prerequisites	Project tools and artifacts
(KEELING; CLEMENTS- CROOME; ROESC, 2015)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Prerequisites	Project tools and artifacts
(LIVERMORE, 2008)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located Team	+	Communication	Communication Quality
(LIVERMORE, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Agile practices	Agile Methodology implementation with large development teams	-	Personnel	Resistance to changes
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Half-cubicles	Hall-cubicles with half-height glass barriers	+	Communication	Communication Quality
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Half-cubicles	Hall-cubicles with half-height glass barriers	+	Communication	Open communication

(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Half-cubicles	Hall-cubicles with half-height glass barriers	+	Organization	Worker availability
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Organization	Worker availability
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Half-cubicles	Hall-cubicles with half-height glass barriers	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Half-cubicles	Hall-cubicles with half-height glass barriers	+	Personnel	Individual work and problem-solving
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Half-cubicles	Hall-cubicles with half-height glass barriers	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Individual workspaces	Individual workspaces	+	Personnel	Individual work and problem-solving
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Individual workspaces	Individual workspaces	+	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Individual workspaces	Individual workspaces	+	Personnel	Worker mental health
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Meeting Spaces	Communal/Discussion Space	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Meeting Spaces	Communal/Discussion Space	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Support Tool	Status Boards	Status boards	+	Personnel	Problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA; OSTROVSKA, 2012)	Physical	Support Tool	Status Boards	Status boards	+	Personnel	Individual commitment
(MISHRA, D; MISHRA;	Physical	Support Tool	Status Boards	Status boards	+	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions

OSTROVSKA, 2012)							
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	General Office Space for a small-scale software development organization	+	Communication	Communication Quality
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Half-cubicles	Half-cubicles with half-height glass barriers	+	Communication	Communication Quality
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Remote working	Distributed Team	-	Communication	Communication Quality
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Half-cubicles	Half-cubicles with half-height glass barriers	+	Organization	Worker availability
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	General Office Space for a small-scale software development organization	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	General Office Space for a small-scale software development organization	+	Personnel	Cooperation
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	General Office Space for a small-scale software development organization	+	Personnel	Performance
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Half-cubicles	Half-cubicles with half-height glass barriers	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Meeting Spaces	Communal/Discussion Space	+	Personnel	Problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Private rooms	Private office Space	+	Personnel	Worker mental health
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Environment Use Practices	Shared Spaces	Shared workspaces	+	Personnel	Team shared work
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Support Tool	Status Boards	Status boards	+	Personnel	Problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Physical	Support Tool	Whiteboards	Whiteboards	+	Personnel	Availability of project information, discussions or instructions
(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Remote working	Distributed Team	-	Personnel	Performance

(MISHRA; MISHRA, 2009)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Remote working	Distributed Team	-	Product	Required quality
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Communication	Communication quality
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Communication	Informal communication
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	+	Communication	Stakeholders communication
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Organization	Organizational structure
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Macro-Environment	Multiple teams	Multiple teamwork environment	+	Organization	Worker availability
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open Plan Office	+	Organization	Worker availability
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Self-management	Self-organizing Team	+	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Mobility
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Privacy
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Cellular	Cellular Office	+	Personnel	Worker general satisfaction
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	HoneyComb	HoneyComb hexagonal design - Chill out cell (Relaxation Room)	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection

(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	HoneyComb	HoneyComb hexagonal design - Chill out cell (Relaxation Room)	+	Personnel	Worker mental health
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	HoneyComb	HoneyComb Hexagonal Design - Conference cell	+	Personnel	Privacy
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	HoneyComb	HoneyComb hexagonal design - Development Team Cell	+	Personnel	Mobility
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	HoneyComb	HoneyComb hexagonal design - Development Team Cell	+	Personnel	People interaction
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	HoneyComb	HoneyComb hexagonal design - Development Team Cell	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	HoneyComb	HoneyComb hexagonal design - Development Team Cell	+	Personnel	Worker mental health
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	HoneyComb	HoneyComb hexagonal design - Product Owner Cell	+	Personnel	Problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	HoneyComb	HoneyComb hexagonal design - Product Owner Cell	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	HoneyComb	HoneyComb hexagonal design - Product Owner Cell	+	Personnel	Mobility
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Meeting Spaces	Scrum Meeting Dedicated Space	+	Personnel	Problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Mobility
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Performance
(ROLA; KUCHTA;	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open Plan Office with (good levels of Acustical/Visual privacy)	+	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions

KOPCZYK, 2016)							
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open Plan Office with (Lower levels of Acustical/Visual privacy)	-	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(ROLA; KUCHTA; KOPCZYK, 2016)	Physical	Support Tool	Whiteboards	Whiteboards	+	Personnel	Availability of project information, discussions or instructions
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Business	Construction costs
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Private rooms	Traditional offices	-	Communication	Informal communication
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Collective meetings	Collective Meetings	+	Management	Organizational alignment
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Organization	Organizational culture
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Collective meetings	Technical presentations	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Collective meetings	Technical presentations	+	Personnel	General learning
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Job rotation	Rotation of Teams' Members	+	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Job rotation	Rotation of Teams' Members	+	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Job rotation	Rotation of Teams' Members	-	Personnel	Worker mental health
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions

(SANTOS et al., 2013)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Mobility
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open Plan Office	-	Personnel	Worker mental health
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Pair programming	Pair programming among different teams	+	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(SANTOS et al., 2013)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Pair programming	Pair programming among different teams	+	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	-	Communication	Informal communication
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	+	Management	Project management
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	-	Organization	Office arrangement and organization
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located Agile team	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located Agile team	+	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located Agile team	+	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located Agile team	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	+	Personnel	Availability of project information, discussions or instructions
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	-	Personnel	Collaboration

(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	-	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	+	Personnel	Self-organization
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	-	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	-	Personnel	Team awareness
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Co-located Agile team	+	Prerequisites	Project tools and artifacts
(SHARP; GIUFFRIDA; MELNIK, 2012)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	-	Prerequisites	Project tools and artifacts
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	-	Communication	Reliability of Information
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	-	Communication	Reliability of Information
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	-	Communication	Reliability of Information
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	-	Communication	Reliability of Information
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	+	Management	Work visibility
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	+	Management	Work visibility
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	+	Personnel	Availability of project information, discussions or instructions

(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	+	Personnel	Problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	+	Personnel	Flexibility to teamwork activities
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	+	Personnel	Individual commitment
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	+	Personnel	Availability of project information, discussions or instructions
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	+	Personnel	Problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	+	Personnel	Flexibility to teamwork activities
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	+	Personnel	Individual commitment
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	Physical	Support Tool	Information Wall	Information Wall	-	Organization	Physical storage capacity

(SHARP; ROBINSON, 2008)	N/A	Software Engineering Practices	Story cards	Story Cards	-	Organization	Physical storage capacity
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	+	Communication	Open communication
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Remote working	Distributed Team	-	Communication	Communication quality
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	+	Customer	Customer relationship
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Large team collocation	-	Management	Project management
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	+	Management	Coordination
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	+	Management	Project management
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	-	Management	Project management
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Remote working	Distributed Team	-	Management	Coordination
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	+	Personnel	Conflicts resolution
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	+	Personnel	People Interaction
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	+	Personnel	Performance
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	-	Personnel	Privacy
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	+	Personnel	Team commitment
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	+	Personnel	Visual or acoustic distractions
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	-	Personnel	Worker general health
(TEASLEY et al., 2002)	Physical	Micro-Environment	Collocation	Single room team collocation	-	Personnel	Worker mental health
(TRAN; BIDDLE, 2009)	Physical	Software Engineering Practices	Face-to-face communication	Face-to-face communication	-	Communication	Reviewability of communication
(TRAN; BIDDLE, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Management	Work planning

(TRAN; BIDDLE, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Organization	Worker availability
(TRAN; BIDDLE, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Collaboration
(TRAN; BIDDLE, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Fruitful discussions, ideation, innovation and reflection
(TRAN; BIDDLE, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	General learning
(TRAN; BIDDLE, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	-	Personnel	Privacy
(TRAN; BIDDLE, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Team awareness
(TRAN; BIDDLE, 2009)	Physical	Layout Pattern	Open Plan	Open plan office	+	Personnel	Team commitment
(TRAN; BIDDLE, 2009)	Virtual	Software Engineering Practices	Agile Methods	Distributed Agile Team	-	Personnel	Shared knowledge and information

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Survey Questionnaire

Demographics Questions

1. What is your e-mail address?
(Open response)
2. What is your name?
(Open response)
3. How old are you?
(Open response)
4. What is your education level?
 - a) High school
 - b) College incomplete
 - c) College complete
 - d) Post-graduation incomplete
 - e) Post-graduation complete
5. Is the company you are working for involved in software development activities?
(Yes, No)
6. What is your job title level?
(Open response)
7. How many years of experience do you have in similar positions?
(Open response)
8. How long have you been working for your current employer?
(Open response)
9. What is the approximate number of employees that the company you work for have?
 - a) Less than 50,
 - b) between 50 and 200,
 - c) between 200 and 500,
 - d) between 500 and 1.000,
 - e) between 1.000 and 10.000
 - f) More than 10.000

Question about the type of work environment

Which option represents the type of office layout that you are current working on?

A

B

C

D

E

F

- a) Open spaces with desks without barriers,
- b) Open spaces with desks composed by half-height lateral or frontal barriers
- c) High cubicles
- d) Half-height cubicles
- e) Enclosed/private spaces
- f) Coworking spaces
- g) Other

Questions about the work environment

Alternatives to questions 1 to 45

- a) strongly disagree b) disagree c) neutral d) agree e) strongly agree

Within the context of Communication

1. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates communication quality.
2. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates informal communication.
3. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates open communication.

4. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working provides positive aspects about information reliability.
5. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates communication with stakeholders.

Within the context of Personnel

6. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates the resolution of individual conflicts.
7. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates the resolution of team conflicts.
8. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working helps with problem resolution, clarification of ideas or pending questions.
9. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates collaboration.
10. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working increases self-confidence.
11. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working increases team confidence.
12. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working allows flexibility for teamwork.
13. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working encourages healthy discussions.
14. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates individual learning.
15. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates team learning.
16. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates individual commitment.
17. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates team commitment.
18. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working is adequate to perform individual work activities.
19. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working is adequate to perform teamwork activities.

20. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates mobility.
21. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates interaction between people.
22. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working increases individual performance.
23. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working increases the team performance.
24. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working provides acceptable levels of privacy.
25. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working has a positive effect on the resistance to change.
26. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working promotes self-organization.
27. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates knowledge and information sharing.
28. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working promotes team awareness about processes, tools, and activities.
29. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working inhibits visual and acoustic distractions.
30. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working improves efficiency to perform work activities.
31. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working increases individual satisfaction.
32. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working increases team satisfaction.
33. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working is adequate for an employee's mental health.
34. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working is adequate for employee's general health.

Within the context of Management

35. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates the organizational alignment.

36. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates coordination.

37. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates work planning (chronograms, scope, capacity, activities, etc).

38. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working provides effective support for leadership.

39. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working increases the visibility of work in progress.

40. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates project management.

Within the context of Organization

41. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working presents positive aspects related to physical space and facilities.

42. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working makes workers easily visible or accessible.

43. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working presents an adequate physical arrangement in relation to the work area.

44. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working facilitates cooperation between different work environments.

45. The workplace layout of the company where I'm currently working is essential to organizational structure.